

Event metadata

Event title	Australian Microbiome – enabling insights into environmental microbial ecosystems
Event type	Webinar
Date of event	15/04/2026
Time of event	12pm AEDT
Topic description	<p>Global microbial atlas initiatives are transforming our understanding of the distribution, function, and ecological roles of microorganisms. However, significant geographic and environmental blind spots remain, particularly in Southern Hemisphere ecosystems and remote coastal or marine environments.</p> <p>Australian BioCommons is proud to highlight how the Australian Microbiome (AM) initiative is addressing this gap. By providing a uniquely comprehensive, national-scale dataset of ~14,000 samples, AM offers researchers access to standardised workflows and rich environmental metadata spanning Australia’s vast climatic gradients.</p> <p>Join Dr Andrew Bisset from CSIRO as he demonstrates how AM enhances our capacity to detect macroecological trends and track environment-critical microbial responses to climate and land-use change. You will see how this initiative strengthens global atlas efforts and provides the tools necessary to characterise novel microbial diversity.</p>
Format description	Webinar presentation followed by a brief question and answer session
Identifier(s)/URL	https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/australian-microbiome-2026
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Keywords	Microbiome

	<p>environmental metadata eDNA Bioinformatics http://edamontology.org/topic_0091</p>
Contact	training@biocommons.org.au
Audience	This webinar is for life science researchers, ecologists, and bioinformaticians who want to leverage large-scale, standardised environmental microbiome datasets and online exploration tools for their own research.
Prerequisites	None
Technical requirements	None
Learning outcomes	<p>By the end of this webinar you should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify how the Australian Microbiome initiative addresses geographic blind spots in global microbial data. • Navigate online data exploration tools to access standardised environmental datasets. • Explain how national-scale microbial data is used to track responses to climate and land-use change.
Speakers	Dr Andrew Bissett, CSIRO
Training materials	<p>Materials shared in this Zenodo record: Presentation slides: AM_APRIL_22026_shared</p> <p>Materials shared elsewhere: YouTube recording: https://youtu.be/Ddaid4tPXXI</p>
Related material	None